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Reaction of Azlactone with Aromatic Ketimines

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Manuscript received 18 August, 1978, accepted 22 December 1978

REACTION of azlactones, which are obtained from α -acylamido acids *in situ*, and carbonyl compounds¹ constitutes the well known Perkin reaction. Cinnamalanilines and azlactones have shown to undergo (4+2)-cycloaddition reaction². A study of this reaction with aromatic ketimines is reported in this communication.

Crystalline products were obtained by the reaction of azlactone of benzoylglycine with ketimines³ of acetophenone, *p*-bromoacetophenone and *o*-hydroxyacetophenone under Perkin conditions (acetic anhydride and sodium acetate). Elemental analysis coupled with the study of IR, NMR and mass spectra supported structures (III) assigned to the products.

IR spectrum of compound IIIa showed bands at 1750 cm^{-1} and 1670 cm^{-1} indicative of carbonyl group and C=N-linkage respectively. NMR spectrum of the compound IIIb showed three methyl protons as a singlet at 7.6 τ and nine aromatic protons as a multiplet between 2.3-2.6 τ . Mass spectrum of compound IIIc showed molecular ion peak at *m/e* 321 as the parent peak. This peak showed that acylation of OH group also took place. The M^+ ion underwent predominantly α -fission of the C-O bond of the acetyl carbonyl to yield a diradical ion $C_{13}H_{15}O_3N$ (*m/e* 278) and CH_3CO^+ (*m/e* 43). The former on decarbonylation with simultaneous elimination of C_6H_5NO as neutral species gave $C_6H_5CO^+$ ion (*m/e* 105). The latter underwent further decarbonylation to yield $C_6H_5^+$ (*m/e* 77) which showed characteristic fission of benzene nucleus. The mass spectrum also indicated the alternative C_6H_5 radical elimination to $C_{13}H_{10}O_4N^+$ ion (*m/e* 244). The mass fragmentation (Chart I) pattern of the product is consistent with its formulation as an azlactone.

The products IIIa-IIIc are found to be identical (m.m.p) with authentic samples of 2-phenyl-4-(α -methylbenzal)-5-oxazolone, 2-phenyl-4-(α -methyl-*p*-bromobenzal)-5-oxazolone and 2-phenyl-4-(α -methyl-*o*-acetoxybenzal)-5-oxazolone synthesised by an unambiguous route.

Chart-1

The formation of III is possible through the electrophilic addition of the enolate, formed by the abstraction of a proton by base from the active methylene function of the azlactone, to the ketimine to give an unstable addition compound (II). Elimination of the amine in the presence of base affords III as shown in Chart 2.

- IIIa, R = H
- IIIb, R = *p*-Br
- IIIc, R = *o*-OOCCH₃

Chart-2

Experimental

Reaction of Azlactone(I) with α -methylbenzalbenzylamine :

Benzoylglycine (0.01 mole) and α -methylbenzalbenzylamine (0.01 mole) were dissolved in dry benzene (50 ml). To this acetic anhydride (AR, 1.2 ml) and sodium acetate (0.5 g) were added. The mixture was just heated to get a clear solution and left at room temperature for 2 days. During this period

most of the product got precipitated, which was filtered off. The mother liquor on concentration gave more of the product IIIa. This product was recrystallised from hot benzene to give pure IIIa, m.p. 203° (yield 72%).

IIIb and IIIc were prepared in similar manner and data for these products are given in Table 1.

Compd. No.	m.p.*	Yield	Molecular formula**
IIIa	203	72%	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ NO ₂
IIIb	245	65%	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ NO ₂ Br
IIIc	225	50%	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ NO ₄

* All the melting points are uncorrected.
** All the compounds gave satisfactory elemental analysis.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to C.S.I.R., New Delhi for awarding PDF to Dr. M. R. and J. R. F. to S.K.

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A New Degradation of Atisine to C₂₀-aminocarbinol

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Manuscript received 18 August 1978, accepted 22 December 1978

VON Braun cyanogen bromide reaction has been employed by a number of workers for the degradation of alkaloids during structure elucidation^{1,2}. The reaction proceeds by an attack at the basic tertiary nitrogen atom. The reagent usually effects the C-N bond cleavage on the less hindered side to yield an alkylbromide and a disubstituted cyanamide. The latter on acid or alkali hydrolysis yields a secondary amine, thus providing a useful procedure for N-dealkylation.

Survey of literature shows no report on the reaction of cyanogen bromide with atisine. It was, therefore, considered of interest to explore this reaction in case of atisine. For the present study atisine (asatsinium chloride (I) (C₂₂H₃₄N⁺O₂Cl⁻), m.p. 311°) was subjected to reduction with sodium borohydride according to the method of Edward to yield dihydroatisine (II) C₂₂H₃₅NO₂, m.p. 161-161.5°,

M⁺m/e 345³. The latter on subsequent reaction with cyanogen bromide in dry solvent ether at room temperature for 24 hours gave an N-nitrile(III), crystallised from absolute ethanol, C₂₁H₃₀N₂O, m.p. 265° in 86% yield.

$\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{KBr}}$ cm⁻¹ 3336 (OH); 1643, 892 (C=CH₂); 1079, 1067 (>CH-OH). No bands assignable to C≡N group could be noted in the IR spectrum. The mass spectrum of III does not show any parent peak, but a M-54 peak (m/e 272) due to C₁₅H₁₁O⁺ in 100 per cent. abundance indicating an initial loss of CH₂=N-C≡N as neutral species from the highly unstable M⁺. Further loss of C₄-Me as a radical gives C₁₁H₇O⁺ (m/e 257) which suffers Retro Diels-Alder cleavage of the bicyclo-octane system comprising rings C and D with loss of CH₂=CH₂ to yield C₁₀H₇O⁺ species (m/e 229). The latter (after rearrangement) undergoes fission along path 'a' or 'b' to yield C₉H₇O⁺ (m/e 135), C₈H₅⁺ (m/e 121), C₈H₁₁⁺ (m/e 107), C₇H₉⁺ (m/e 93) and C₆H₇⁺ (m/e 79) species as other prominent peaks. The fragmentation pattern of III is given in chart 1.

A study of the mass spectrum of dihydroatisine shows a similar fragmentation pattern. The M⁺ ion C₂₂H₃₅NO₂ (m/e 345) suffers a loss of C₂₂ carbon as CH₂OH radical to give a M-31 ion radical C₂₁H₃₃NO⁺ peak at m/e 314 in 100 per cent. abundance. The latter then undergoes the fission of hetero ring E to yield the same C₁₀H₇O⁺ species (m/e 272) as observed in the mass spectrum of III. Similar fragmentation pattern further confirm the similar position of the rings A, B, C, D and E in the known pentacyclic skeleton in both cases.

Acid hydrolysis of III with 10% boiling HCl for about 2 hours followed by extraction with ether after basification with alkali gave on evaporation the crude C₂₀-aminocarbinol(IV). The latter was purified by passing through a column of activated

